

ISic3572

Dedication by Paccius

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

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Autopsy

2011.06.15

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Halaesa

Place of origin (modern)

near Castel di Tusa

Provenance

Excavated in 1971, in room 7 of the west portico of the agora

Coordinates

37.997856, 14.262463

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Halaesa, Antiquarium e sito archeologico di Halaesa, inventory 30599

Physical Description

Fragment of off-white marble. Part of the upper edge is intact, but the stone is broken on the other three sides. Both front and rear surfaces are well finished. There are a few plaster traces on the reverse.

Dimensions

Height 34.2 cm

Width 34.6 cm

Depth 1.8-2.7 cm

Layout

There is a substantial vacat between the top margin and the first line of letters. Remains of three lines of text survive, although only traces of two letters remain from the third line.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

The letters are simply cut, with light serifs. They are moderately well proportioned, but show some irregularity (especially in line 2). P is not closed. Elegant interpuncts are visible between all word breaks, triangular developing towards the form of a leaf (hedera).

Letter heights:

Line 1: 68-73 mm

Line 2: 53-55 mm

Line 3: incomplete mm

Interlineation

Interlineation: not measured mm

Text

1. [---]divi · Aug[usti][---]
2. [---]· Paccius · M[(arci)f(ilius)][---]
3. [---] · [---]

Apparatus

Text from autopsy

Translation

Commentary

The most likely resolution of the phrase *Divi Augusti* in the first line is a dedication to Tiberius Caesar *divi Augusti filius Augustus*. In any case, the presence of *divi Augusti* provides a *terminus post quem* of AD 14. A dedication to Tiberius is known from nearby Capo d'Orlando, ancient Agathyrnum (ISic3339 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3339>]). Paccius is a common Latin name of Oscan derivation. The name is rarely attested in Sicily: an individual of Oscan origin at Entella in the third century BC (Entella tablets C1 [www.trismegistos.org/text/699040] , C2 [www.trismegistos.org/text/699041] , C3 [www.trismegistos.org/text/699042]); but more importantly on the municipal coinage of Halaesa itself, where one Marcus Paccius Maximus is recorded as both *duovir* and *flamen Augusti* (*designatus*) (RPC I, nos. 630-633, of Augustan date, e.g. ANS 2015.20.550 [<http://numismatics.org/collection/2015.20.550>]). Paccius son of Marcus in line 2 of this inscription could refer either to the same individual as that on the coinage, or a relative (such as his son). A dedication to Tiberius by either M. Paccius Maximus himself, or e.g. his son would be entirely plausible (see Facella 2006: 208-210 and 273-74 for M. Paccius Maximus, in the context of extensive Campanian connections to Halaesa).

In line 3, traces of two letters and at least one interpunct survive. The first letter is either Q or O (D is unlikely from the traces on the stone); the second letter is either E or F. There may be a trace of an interpunct surviving just before the vertical hasta of the second letter, although the space is limited; this would encourage a reading of Q · F ·, i.e. Q(uinti) f(ilius), suggesting that line three carries another personal name in the nominative, and so a second dedicant responsible for the text (e.g. a fellow magistrate or priest). Alternatively, if we read OE at the end of a word, this is most likely a female name such as Callirhoe or Zoe (and so perhaps the wife, mother, or daughter of Paccius). The alternatives OF and QE are implausible in Latin.

See ISic3581 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3581>] for a second text which may be erected by the same individual.

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Bibliography

Prag, J.R.W., Tigano, G. 2017. Alesa Archonidea : il lapidarium. *Introduzione all'archeologia di Halaesa*. Palermo. At no.20

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